

The development of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania, 1555-1588¹

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Abstract

This paper maps the history of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania between 1558 and 1588 by outlining the origins and tenets of Christians rejecting the doctrine of the Trinity as well as analysing the denomination's spread and radicalisation in the East Central European region. It argues that Antitrinitarians in the second half of the sixteenth century achieved a prominent status at the Transylvanian court due to their personal good relations with the rulers and the relative religious tolerance of the principality. Thus, this paper sheds light on the exceptional influence of a Protestant community in the age of fierce religious persecutions across Europe.

Images 1 and 2 (next page): Unitarian church (Homoródszentpéter/Petreni in modern-day Romania)²

¹ I would like to thank Dr. Lionel Laborie (Institute for History, Leiden University) for his valuable advice in the spring of 2020 in the course of writing the paper which served as the basis of this article.

² Wikimedia Commons, 2015, accessed May 15, 2020.

Introduction

In 1517, Martin Luther's theses criticised the pursuits and activities of the papacy and challenged several Roman Catholic principles. The escalating theological debates induced the appearance of numerous reform movements that formed parts of a comprehensive European phenomenon. Theological disagreements within the Protestant Reformation led to the birth of several different creeds and denominations. One radical branch, Antitrinitarianism, rejected the Holy Trinity and Christ's divinity, and East Central Europe proved to be the only place in the continent where it could develop successfully. Antitrinitarianism was introduced in Transylvania by Italian individuals in the 1550s and 1560s. It started to spread at the court and among the wider population, under the reign of its religiously tolerant prince, John Sigismund (1559-1571). By the late 1570s, theological disputes between Giorgio Biandrata (1515-1588) and Ferenc Dávid (1520-1579), the leaders of Transylvanian Antitrinitarians, resulted in an unprecedented religious conflict in the community. Nonetheless, the Antitrinitarian denomination has survived and is present in Transylvania even today.

This paper addresses the question: What role did the Antitrinitarian movement play in the religious plurality and in the process of confessionalisation in Transylvania between 1555 and 1588? The aim of this paper is to analyse how Antitrinitarianism was accepted in Transylvania, and how Antitrinitarians contributed to the religious and intellectual life of the principality in the sixteenth century.

Antitrinitarianism has attracted the curiosity of various scholars in the past centuries due to the role of Transylvania as a ‘religious melting pot’. First, Antitrinitarian history interested Unitarian³ intellectuals who approached the topic from a specifically religious perspective, for instance Earl Morse Wilbur.⁴ In the 1960s, an increased attention was paid to Antitrinitarianism in a transnational context, due to the publication of a series on the Italian Reformation, the *Biblioteca del Corpus Reformatorum Italicorum*. One of its volumes, authored by Delio Cantimori, dealt with the activities of sixteenth-century Italian ‘heretics’ in the Swiss cantons, the Holy Roman Empire, and Eastern Europe.⁵ His research was improved by Domenico Caccamo’s analysis of the ‘heretical’ thinking of Italians specifically in Transylvania, Poland-Lithuania,⁶ and Moravia. Caccamo has argued that the progress of these radical trends was dependent on the gradually changing political environment of the area.⁷ These scholars found the origin of Antitrinitarianism in the theology of Michael Servetus (1511-1553), but this concept was challenged by Andrew M. Hill. He has stated that its chief source was Calvinism since Antitrinitarian communities both in Poland-Lithuania and Transylvania were established after their breaks with the local Calvinist congregations.⁸ Howard Hotson has regarded Antitrinitarian thinkers as the philosophical forerunners of the Enlightenment by attributing the most progressive ideas of the context of the Reformation and the Renaissance, reason, freedom, tolerance, to them.⁹ Gábor Almási has highlighted that Antitrinitarians emphasised the Old

³ The Unitarian Church of Transylvania is the institutionalised form of Antitrinitarianism. Since this name became widely used from the seventeenth century, I refer to the community by using the term ‘Antitrinitarian’ in this paper.

⁴ Earl Morse Wilbur, *A history of Unitarianism*, 1 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1945).

⁵ Delio Cantimori, *Eretici italiani del Cinquecento. Ricerche storiche* (Florence: Sansoni, 1967), 320–330.

⁶ The Kingdom of Poland and the Grand Duchy of Lithuania was a dual state (1569-1575), officially unified in 1569 by Sigismund II Augustus (1548-1572). Nonetheless, Sigismund I the Old (1506-1548) had already ruled both states. Therefore, I use the term ‘Poland-Lithuania’ in this paper.

⁷ Domenico Caccamo, *Eretici italiani in Moravia, Polonia, Transilvania* (Florence: Sansoni, 1970), 22–31, 109–151.

⁸ Andrew M. Hill, “Why Unitarian-Universalists owe more to John Calvin than they do to Michael Servetus,” *Keresztény Magvető* 109 (2003): 143–152.

⁹ Howard Hotson, “Arianism and Millenarianism: The Link Between the Two Heresies from Servetus to Socinus,” in *Continental Millenarians: Protestants, Catholics, Heretics*, ed. by John Christian Laursen and Richard H. Popkin (Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001), 9–35.

Testament and the importance of Hebrew and Syrian studies in theological education.¹⁰

Similarly, Nicholas Terpstra has asserted that from the 1580s, Antitrinitarian intellectuals had followed the humanistic ideal of reading the Bible in original languages in order to get more trustworthy interpretations.¹¹

The concept most central to this paper is religious radicalism. The term ‘radical’, both in political and religious senses, has been defined in various ways, such as a fundamental political or social reform, a distinctive behaviour and a renewing activity. Ariel Hessayon and David Finnegan have argued that the borders between ‘radical’ and ‘mainstream’ phenomena are often not solid, and therefore, each case study should be contextualised.¹² I agree with the interpretation of ‘radicalism’ as a relative and anachronistic label which started to be used in modern times. Consequently, I use the term religious radicalism in the framework of the theological disagreements and doctrinal differences that distinguished Antitrinitarians from Catholics and Calvinists.

The approach of this research is political. It aims to carry out a qualitative investigation of primary sources to map the turning points of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania. It focuses on information with historical rather than theological value, and on references to political events to delineate the circumstances of theological radicalisation and the relations of Antitrinitarian leaders with a Protestant as well as a Catholic ruler. Antitrinitarians’ writings will be used to explicate why they were seen as ‘heresy’, while resolutions of the Transylvanian Diet will be

¹⁰ Gábor Almási, “Andreas Dudith (1533-1589): Conflicts and strategies of a religious individualist in confessionalising Europe,” in *Between Scylla and Charybdis: Learned Letter Writers Navigating the Reefs of Religious and Political Controversy in Early Modern Europe*, ed. by Jeanine de Landtsheer and Henk Nellen (Leiden: Brill, 2011), 161–184.

¹¹ Nicholas Terpstra, *Religious Refugees in the Early Modern World* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 155–156.

¹² Ariel Hessayon and David Finnegan, eds., *Varieties of Seventeenth- and Eighteenth-Century English Radicalism in Context* (Farnham: Ashgate, 2011), 10–15.

examined to trace down the stages of the political acceptance of Antitrinitarians.¹³ The accounts of oral theological polemics and written disputations will be examined to outline the statements and refutations between Antitrinitarian and Calvinist thinkers. The main obstacle when analysing these are their length so this paper will focus on parts that had the most significant political implications.

Thus, this paper offers a contribution to the scholarship on a radical branch of the Protestant Reformation, which flourished in Transylvania in the era of common religious persecutions throughout Europe. The paper aims to demonstrate that Antitrinitarianism succeeded and survived in Transylvania due to the social and religious diversity of the territory, and to the continental political situation that made toleration necessary for stability to be preserved. The first part of the paper is dedicated to the introduction of Antitrinitarianism's appearance in Europe in the 1550s, the second covers its Transylvanian history until 1571, and the third section concentrates on the process of radicalisation up to the late 1580s.

¹³ Transylvania was a semi-independent *elective monarchy* where the *estates* (Hungarian nobles, Saxon patricians, Szekler soldiers) had a considerable say in governmental issues at diet assemblies. See Teréz Oborni, "State and governance in the Principality of Transylvania," *Hungarian Studies* 27 (2013), 313–324.

The origins, doctrines, and early spread of Antitrinitarianism in the 1550s

Image 3: Christian Fritsch,
Michael Servetus (c.1740)

¹⁴ Antitrinitarianism was born out of the theories of several individuals in the course of the sixteenth century. The first Antitrinitarians were Spanish and Italian Protestant intellectuals who revived the ancient principles of Arianism – the denial of Christ’s divinity and the dogma of the Holy Trinity. In the first part of this paper, it is worth looking at why Antitrinitarianism can be defined as a ‘radical’ religious belief, and how it was dealt with by the Catholic Church and by other Protestants in the 1550s.

The first important figure of Antitrinitarianism was Michael Servetus. The Spanish humanist was a physician and a theologian, and his writings testify to the great extent to which his two professions were intertwined. During his anatomical training in Paris in the 1530s, Servetus elaborated a theory according to which the Holy Spirit deifies human beings through their breathing.¹⁵ His arguments largely contributed to the study of pulmonary circulation, the exchange of deoxygenated and oxygenated blood between the heart and the lungs.¹⁶ In 1531, Servetus summarised his arguments for the ‘errors’ of the Trinity in *De Trinitatis erroribus* which became the Christological basis of a new belief system:

¹⁴ Wikimedia Commons, 2017, accessed May 15, 2020.

¹⁵ Michael Servetus, *Christianismi Restitutio* (Vienne, 1553), 171 – Digital Imaging Unit, Edinburgh University Library, accessed May 11, 2020, <https://images.is.ed.ac.uk/luna/servlet/view/search;JSESSIONID=3ec3dc7c-41a1-4481-9dea-04e82a75fede?q=Df.8.90&os=0&pgs=250&res=0>.

¹⁶ Elizabeth Martin and Robert Hine, *A dictionary of biology*, 6th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 540.

Christ, being one with Yahweh his Father, equal in power, came down from heaven and assumed flesh as a man. In short, all the Scriptures speak of Christ as a man.¹⁷

Servetus described his medical observations in a 1553 theological book titled *Christianismi Restitutio*, and denied the concepts of the Trinity, the original sin, and the predestination.¹⁸ Thus, Servetus challenged basic Catholic teachings along with the tenets of the French reformer John Calvin (1509-1564) which were noted in ‘Chapter XIII. One Divine Essence, Containing Three Persons; Taught In The Scriptures From The Beginning’ in the first book of Calvin’s *Institutes of the Christian Religion* (1536).¹⁹ Eventually, Servetus was burnt at the stake in the Calvinist Republic of Geneva for his ‘heretical’ views in October 1553.

Servetus’s thoughts spread quickly in the religiously relatively tolerant Republic of Venice, particularly in the academic circles of the University of Padua, which had not been confined by a severe religious supervision.²⁰ Matteo Gribaldi Moffa (1505-1564) was a Piedmontese law professor at Padua and a leading figure of local Protestants and religious refugees from German territories. Gribaldi had been in contact with the Italian community in Geneva, supported the ideas of Servetus, and was even present at his trial in 1553. Gribaldi moved to Geneva in 1555, but soon found himself in the opposition of Calvin for rejecting the theory of predestination and sympathising with Servetian thoughts. As expressed in his brochure *De vera Dei et filius eius cognitione*. Gribaldi believed that the divine Trinity was an invention of men in the first centuries of Christianity that had no foundation in the Scriptures.²¹ Gribaldi left for Tübingen

¹⁷ Michael Servetus, *De Trinitatis erroribus* (Hagenau, 1531) quoted in English in Earl Morse Wilbur, ed., *The two treatises of Servetus on the Trinity* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1932), 3.

¹⁸ Published in Vienne, France.

¹⁹ John Allen, ed., *Institutes of the Christian Religion by John Calvin* (Philadelphia: Presbyterian Board of Publication, 1813), 140–186.

²⁰ On the history of the University of Padua, see Lucia Rossetti, *The University of Padua. An Outline of Its History* (Trieste: Edizioni Lint, 1983); and Piero Del Negro, *L’Università di Padova: otto secoli di storia* (Padova: Signum, 2001).

²¹ Delio Cantimori and Elizabeth Feist, eds., *Per la storia degli eretici italiani del secolo XVI in Europa. Studi e documenti*, 11 (Rome: Reale Accademia d’Italia, 1937), 81.

where he published a pamphlet titled *Apologia pro Michaele Serveto* in which he defended the executed reformer.²² Gribaldi became persecuted by the university council, so he fled to Farges in the Kingdom of France. In 1559, the professor started to teach at the University of Grenoble, but due to an investigation ordered against him, he returned to Farges, where he died in 1564.²³

Gribaldi's Antitrinitarian ideas influenced many other intellectuals, notably Polish theologian Petrus Gonesius (1525-1573) who studied philosophy and then taught logic at Padua. Antitrinitarian works were taken into Poland-Lithuania by Gonesius in 1555. He objected to the dogma of the Trinity at the Synod of the Polish Reformed Church in January 1556.²⁴ Gonesius was excommunicated but managed to gain some supporters. In 1565, the theological disagreements within the Polish Reformed Church led to a split between the Calvinists and the Antitrinitarian faction. In 1565, the latter group reorganised themselves with the leadership of Gonesius as the Polish Brethren or *Ecclesia minor*, that is to say the Minor Reformed Church of Poland.²⁵

Gribaldi's other colleague, with whom he collaborated to develop his Antitrinitarian ideas in Padua, was Lelio Sozzini (1525-1562), a humanist reformer from Siena.²⁶ He started his education as a lawyer in Bologna and Padua but soon moved to Vicenza in the Republic of Venice. Here he became involved in the gatherings of a Protestant group, the *Collegia Vicentina*

²² Piet Visser, ed., *Bibliographia Sociniana: A Bibliographical Reference Tool for the Study of Dutch Socinianism and Antitrinitarianism* (Amsterdam: Hilversum, 2004), 13.

²³ Frederic C. Church, *I riformatori italiani*, 2 (Milan: Il Saggiatore, 1967), 179–182.

²⁴ The Polish Reformed Church was founded in 1551 and followed the Calvinist trend in theological and organisational aspects.

²⁵ Ralf Bröer, “Blutkreislauf und Dreieinigkeit Medizinischer Antitrinitarismus von Michael Servet (1511–1553) bis Giorgio Biandrata (1515–1588),” *Berichte zur Wissenschaftsgeschichte* 29: (2006), 21–37.

²⁶ Earl Morse Wilbur, *A history of Unitarianism*, 1 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1945), 81.

or Fratres vicentini who professed Anabaptist²⁷ and Antitrinitarian doctrines. Lelio frequently traveled abroad to preach his thoughts, and conducted vivid correspondence with John Calvin, raising his doubts concerning the Trinity, the predestination, and the resurrection of the body.²⁸ Suspected of following Servetian principles, Lelio was persecuted by the Roman Inquisition. After 1555, he could not return to Italy and died in Zürich in 1562.

Lelio's nephew, Fausto Sozzini (1539-1604) continued his uncle's exploration of biblical texts, European travels, and participation in theological debates. In 1579, he settled down in Poland-Lithuania and became the leader of the Polish Brethren. He believed that Christ could be addressed in prayers only indirectly as a mediator between people and the Father. In addition, he strived for simplifying Christian dogmas exclusively on the basis of the Bible. In 1578, Fausto completed his chief work, the *De Jesu Christo Servatore*, in which he argued that Christ's death had not made a full satisfaction for sins since only the Father could decide which sins would be forgiven – otherwise the 'delinquent would not have a true repentance but a fear of punishment'.²⁹ Fausto Sozzini's theological statements were highly influential in the later development of Antitrinitarianism in Poland-Lithuania. The term Socinianism stands for the system of tenets evolved in the Polish Brethren along the ideas of Lelio and Fausto Sozzini, and is derived from the Latinising version of their surname, Socinus.

²⁷ Anabaptists, members of another branch of the Radical Reformation, proclaimed that baptism should be preceded by a confession of faith, and therefore, rejected the baptism of infants.

²⁸ Luisa Simonutti, "Locke's Biblical Hermeneutics on Bodily Resurrection," in Luisa Simonutti, ed., *Locke and Biblical Hermeneutics. Conscience and Scripture* (New York: Springer International Publishing, 2019), 55–74.

²⁹ '... delinquentis non veram poenitentiam, sed poenae formidinem...' in Fausto Sozzini, *De Jesu Christo Servatore* (Krakow: Alexi Rodeci, 1594), 234, accessed May 10, 2020, <https://books.google.hu/books?id=vy9bAAAAcAAJ&printsec=frontcover&dq=De+Iesu+Christo+Servatore&hl=hu&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwjQ2sn40sDpAhWOpokHwZwAJgQ6AEIKDAA#v=onepage&q=De%20Iesu%20Christo%20Servatore&f=false>.

All in all, the diversity of Antitrinitarian theology originated in the international network of persecuted radicals and their religious activities. Most of them were educated physicians or lawyers who produced radical religious ideas and innovative scientific theories as well.³⁰

Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism, 1559-1571

Transylvania became the most flourishing centre of Antitrinitarianism in the 1560s. It is essential to discuss the political and religious circumstances that attracted Antitrinitarians to Transylvania, and the role that Antitrinitarians played at John Sigismund's court.

The name *Transylvania* refers to a historical and geographical area in the East Central European region that was a relatively short-lived semi-independent political territory in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. Until 1526, it had been part of the Kingdom of Hungary, which was divided after the victorious campaign of Suleiman I, sultan of the Ottoman Empire (1520-1566). A lengthy power struggle for total influence over the former royal territories started between the House of Habsburg and the Szapolyai family. The eastern areas were ruled by John I Szapolyai until 1540, by his widow Isabella Jagiellon until 1559, and then by their son John Sigismund (1540-1571). John Sigismund's legitimacy, as it remained the case with later rulers too, was dependent on Ottoman support against the Habsburg rivals who continued contesting the title of Transylvanian rulers in order to unite Hungary under their crown.³¹ In addition to the political challenge of being located between the Habsburg and Ottoman interests of expansion, John Sigismund inherited a land inhabited by Calvinist Hungarians, Lutheran Saxons, Roman Catholic Szeklers, and Eastern Orthodox Christian Romanians.

³⁰ On medicine and the Reformation in Italy, see Alessandra Celati, "*Contra medicos*: Physicians Facing the Inquisition in Sixteenth-Century Venice," in *Medicine and the Inquisition in the Early Modern World*, ed. by Maria Pia Donato (Leiden: Brill, 2019), 72–91.

³¹ László Makkai and András Mócsy, eds., *Erdély története, 1: A kezdetektől 1606-ig* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1986), 409–446.

Image 4: Giorgio Biandrata

³² The protagonist of the Transylvanian expansion was Giorgio Biandrata (1515-1588), a physician from Saluzzo (Piedmont) and alumnus of the University of Montpellier – which was a hotspot of the radical heterodoxy at that time.³³ Biandrata specialised in obstetrics and gynaecology, and issued a pioneering textbook in this field in 1539, in which he summarised Aristotelian gynaecological theories on fertilisation, weight, birth, and childbed.³⁴

Biandrata dedicated this book to Bona Sforza (1494-1557), the wife of Sigismund I the Old of Poland-Lithuania (1467-1548), and a member of the Milanese princely Sforza family, for whom he worked as a personal physician from 1540 until 1544; and to her daughter, the wife of John I Szapolyai of Hungary (1487-1540), Isabella Jagiellon (1519-1559), whom he served as a gynaecologist during the following eight years. In 1551, Biandrata returned to Italy and practiced medicine in Mestre but clashed with the Inquisition for his Antitrinitarian proclamations. Therefore, he fled to Geneva where the ‘Italian exile’ was gradually increasing in the course of the 1550s.³⁵ In 1558, a few theologians of this community frequently expressed their disagreements with Calvin, namely Giovanni Valentino Gentile (c.1520-1566), Gian Paolo Alciati (1515-1573), and Biandrata. They argued for the ‘detachment’ of the persons of the Trinity and the subordination of Christ and the Holy Spirit to the Father. Calvin responded

³² Wikimedia Commons, 2012, accessed May 15, 2020.

³³ Antonio Rotondò, “Giorgio Biandrata,” in *Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani*, 10 (1968), accessed May 20, 2020, http://www.treccani.it/enciclopedia/giovanni-giorgio-biandrata_%28Dizionario-Biografico%29/

³⁴ Giorgio Biandrata, *Gynaecorum ex Aristotele et Bonaciolo a Georgio Blandrata medico Subalpino noviter excerpta de fecundatione, gravitate, partu et puerperio* (Argentinae, 1539).

³⁵ Elek Jakab, “Néhány adat Blandrata György élete és jelleme ismeréséhez,” *Keresztény Magvető* 12: (1877), 1–32, 3-4.

to these theological issues in a letter titled *Responsum ad quaestiones Georgii Blandratae*.³⁶

After being forced to sign a declaration of faith in the Holy Trinity, the ‘rebels’ escaped to Pińczów, Poland-Lithuania, and joined the Polish Reformed Church. Calvin fervently warned his Polish ‘colleagues’ about the danger inherent in the presence of the Antitrinitarians:

Their comments decreased Christ to only a mediator, and thus, interfered with the Trinity... There are filthy loafers with you, Giorgio Biandrata, Valentino Gentile, Gian Paolo Alciati, and others, whose frantic lust leads to innovation and headlong turbulence...³⁷

As Calvin constantly urged the Polish Reformed Church to excommunicate the ‘heretics’, their situation was deteriorating. Biandrata soon found an opportunity to move to Transylvania, while his fellows were expelled from Poland-Lithuania when the 1564 Edict of Parczów forced all foreign Protestants to leave.

In the early modern period, confessionalisation consisted of the evolution of religious beliefs and trends into set denominations along with the consolidation of their doctrines. In Transylvania, the institutionalisation of the different Protestant communities was a relatively slow process. This phenomenon was closely related to a so-called ‘universal Protestantism’ which had characterised the religious atmosphere of Transylvania until the 1560s.³⁸ This condition was the reason for the failure of Francesco Stancaro (1501-1574) when preaching his Antitrinitarian views in Transylvania in the 1550s. Stancaro had been a physician and professor of theology and Hebrew at Padua until he left Italy after a clash with the Inquisition. He

³⁶ Jean-François Gilmont and Peter Rodolphe, eds., *Bibliotheca Calviniana: les oeuvres de Jean Calvin publiées au XVIe siècle III, Écrits théologiques, littéraires et juridiques: 1565-1600*, 3 (Genève: Librairie Droz, 2000), 121-125.

³⁷ ‘Sunt enim apud vos impuri nebulones Georgius Blandrata, Valentinus Gentilis, Ioannes Paulus Alciatus, et similes, quos furiosa libido novandi et turbandi praecipites agit.’ in Edouard Cunitz et al., eds., *Ioannis Calvinii opera quae supersunt omnia*, 9 (Brunsvigae: Schwetschke, 1870), col. 646.

³⁸ Mihály Balázs, “Megjegyzések János Zsigmond valláspolitikához,” in Béla Varjas, ed., *Irodalom és ideológia a 16-17. században* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1987), 67–93, 76-77.

followed Servetian beliefs – denied Christ’s divinity and insisted on using the Bible as the exclusive theological source. In 1554, Stancaro was employed as the physician of Péter Petrovics (c.1486-1557), a Hungarian nobleman and supporter of the Reformation in Transylvania, so he had a chance to preach his views there. In 1555, a synod was held in Szék in order to discuss Antitrinitarian and Lutheran disagreements where Stancaro’s ideas were not accepted.³⁹

In 1563, John Sigismund invited Giorgio Biandrata, known as a loyal member of his mother’s entourage, to become his personal physician and counsellor at the court in Alba Iulia (in Hungarian: Gyulafehérvár), the capital of Transylvania. Thus, the heterogeneous palette of the Transylvanian society received a new colour with Biandrata’s arrival since he got engaged in religious polemics beside his medical commitments.⁴⁰ His main colleague in building the Antitrinitarian community was Ferenc Dávid (1520-1579), a Hungarian superintendent of the Calvinist Reformed Church in Transylvania. Dávid was raised Catholic, then became Lutheran, later Calvinist, and finally Antitrinitarian – his eagerness for theological research drew him from one denomination to another. In 1555, he had rejected Stancaro’s ideas against the Trinity in his writing titled *Dialysis Scripti Stancari Contra Primum Articulum Synodi Szekiensis...* He became John Sigismund’s court pastor still as a Calvinist but his theological versatility and interest in the works of Servetus and the Dutch humanist philosopher Erasmus of Rotterdam (1466-1536) provided fertile soil for Biandrata’s preachings. In 1567, Dávid dedicated his first Antitrinitarian work, the *Refutatio scripti Petri Melii* to ‘Joannes secundus D[ei] g[ratia] elect[us] rex Hungariae Dalmatiae Croatiae’ – this way, he referred to John Sigismund as the king of all the historical (former) territories of Hungary. In this piece, Dávid stated that the ruler

³⁹ Francesco Ruffini, *Studi sui riformatori italiani* (Turin: Edizioni Ramella, 1955), 165-406.

⁴⁰ Vincenzo Malacarne, *Commentario Delle Opere E Delle Vicende Di Giorgio Biandrata Nobile Saluzzese Archiatro In Transilvania E In Polonia* (Padova: Tipografia Bettoni, 1814), 46-50.

had the task to organise synods where the religious debates could be concluded. Moreover, he declared that the spread of Antitrinitarian tenets should be in parallel with the protection of their opponents' beliefs which testifies to his inclination to religious tolerance.⁴¹ An anthology of Antitrinitarian writings, collected and edited by Biandrata and Dávid was published in Alba Iulia in 1568, under the title *De falsa et vera unius Dei patris, filii et spritus sancti cognitione*. Importantly, this volume consisted of Lelio Sozzini's interpretation of the First Epistle of John, titled *Brevis explicatio in primum Iohannis caput*, along with their own shared theological points.⁴²

John Sigismund was personally very interested in theology – he was highly educated, willing to read and hear about religious issues, and spoke several languages thanks to the multilingual court of his Polish-Italian mother, Isabella Jagiellon. Despite being loyal to the Roman Catholic Church in the first years of his reign, John converted to Lutheranism in 1562, became Calvinist soon after, and eventually turned towards Antitrinitarianism in the late 1560s – thanks to the explicit influence of his physician and confidante, Giorgio Biandrata, and his court pastor, Ferenc Dávid.⁴³ John Sigismund was eager to participate in public events where representatives of the different denominations discussed theological issues. His open-minded attitude can be considered another important cause of the 'Antitrinitarian success' – he gained full power from his mother and her counsellors only in 1559 so Stancaró's early attempts in 1555 had been hindered by a solid Catholic leadership. The two Antitrinitarian theologians had a gradually increasing influence over John Sigismund and the nobility, which induced the indignation of

⁴¹ Ferenc Dávid, *Refutatio scripti Petri Melii* (Gyulafehérvár: TRRH, 1567), preface – Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences / MTA, accessed May 14, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/964/7/A_166_VI.pdf

⁴² Antal Pirnát, ed., *De falsa et vera unius Dei patris, filii et spritus sancti cognitione* (Utrecht: Bibliotheca Unitariorum, 1988).

⁴³ István Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe: Ethnic Diversity, Denominational Plurality, and Corporative Politics in the Principality of Transylvania (1526–1691)* (Leiden: Brill, 2009), 99-101.

other churches, particularly the that of the Calvinists. A long series of disputations started between Ferenc Dávid and Péter Méliusz Juhász (1532-1572), bishop of the Calvinist Reformed Church in Transylvania from 1561. Méliusz was engaged in a number of written and oral debates with Dávid on their conflicts about God's unity and the question of the Trinity. The most important encounter of differing Protestant views was the disputation organised in October 1569 in Várad where Méliusz identified Biandrata and Dávid with the sons of the Satan and argued that:

Seventh objection to the sons of Beelzebub

The Pater Noster only mentions the Father, therefore only the Father is to be adored, and the Son is not.

ANSWER: This is a false 'Consequentia'... because I can prove that everything that belongs to the Father, belongs to the Son as well, the Father has never been either a Father or a God without his Son...⁴⁴

At this event, John Sigismund expressed his sympathy with Antitrinitarians as well as his dedication to ensure religious tolerance:

We wish that in our country... freedom shall reign. We know furthermore that faith is a gift from God and that conscience cannot be constrained.⁴⁵

This effort aimed at synthesising the various theological controversies of the country. However, these events did not succeed in bringing together the different views, and the Calvinist and Antitrinitarian tenets became increasingly distinct.⁴⁶ In 1567, John Sigismund established a press house in Alba Iulia for the Antitrinitarians where several works of their leading theologians were published – remarkably, Dávid's *Brief Explanation of how the Antichrist has*

⁴⁴ 'Hetedik ellen vetesek a Belzebub fiaynak. A Pater nosterben csak attiat nevez, Hat csak az attia imadando nem a fia. Felelet: Hamis Consequentia imez harom okert: Első mert meg bizonyitok hogy a my az attiaie mind az fiuie, az attia soha fia nélkül nem volt, sem attia sem isten...' in Péter Méliusz Juhász, *Az egész Szentírásból való igaz tudomány* (Debrecen: András Komlós, 1570), 70 – MTA, accessed May 20, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/303/1/RMK_I_0077-M_0061-b.pdf.

⁴⁵ 'Mert a mű birodalmunkban, ..., mű azt akariuc, Hogy szabaság legyen. Touábba, Tudgyuc, Hogy a hitt Istenec aiándékia, Es a lelki esmeret semmire erőszackal nem vitethetic.' in Lajos Nagy and Domokos Simén, eds., *Unitárius írók a XVI. évszázadból, I: A nagyváradi disputatio* (Kolozsvár, 1870), 130-131.

⁴⁶ Mihály Balázs, *Early Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism (1566-1571): From Servet to Palaeologus* (Baden-Baden: Éditions Valentin Koekner, 1996), 213.

obscured the true knowledge of God, a summary of Antitrinitarian principles. Dávid argued that the Reformation and the purification of Christianity would be perfected by Antitrinitarians and identified Catholic popes as the manifestations of the Antichrist – which was a common topos in contemporary Protestant arguments against the Catholic Church.⁴⁷

The most considerable political advancement of Antitrinitarianism took place in the renowned Diet of Torda which was organised between 6 and 13 January 1568, and attended by John Sigismund. The Transylvanian estates accepted the Edict of Torda which proclaimed the equality of the Roman Catholic, Lutheran, Calvinist, and Antitrinitarian beliefs. These so-called ‘received religions’ were freely chosen and practiced according to the will of each congregation:

The preachers shall preach the Gospel and proclaim it, each according to his own understanding, and if the congregation wants to follow, so be it, if not, no one shall be compelled, for a soul will not find peace in this way, rather every man shall follow the preacher whose teachings appeal to him. For this reason, no superintendent or any other person shall do harm to the preachers; none shall suffer at the hands of others for religious reasons... and it shall be permitted to no one to jail others or ban them because of their teachings, for faith is a gift of God and arises from the hearing that comes from God’s Word.⁴⁸

It is important to mention that the edict did not acknowledge all Christian denominations or the Jewish community, and John Sigismund even took steps to limit the rights of the Catholics. Nevertheless, it was the first document to proclaim the toleration of different and theologically clashing denominations, and thus, one of the most significant political decrees concerning religious issues in early modern Europe – along with the Peace of Augsburg in the Holy Roman Empire (1555), the Edict of Nantes in the Kingdom of France (1598), and the Peace of Westphalia (1648) that ended the Thirty Years’ War (1618-1648). An interesting parallel can

⁴⁷ Ferenc Dávid, *Rövid Magyarazat mikeppen az Antichristus, az igaz Istenről való tudomant meg homalosította* (Gyulafehérvár: TRRH, 1567). Cf: Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 110.

⁴⁸ Quoted in Hungarian in Jenő Zoványi, *A magyar protestantizmus története* (Budapest: Attraktor, 2004, 23; and in English in Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 111.

be drawn between the Edict of Torda and the Sandomierz Agreement which denoted a united Protestant front in Poland-Lithuania between 1570 and 1580 against the Counter Reformation activities of the Roman Catholic Church. However, the Polish Brethren did not participate in the agreement, and the success of this coalition itself was largely limited by the institutional difficulties that the radical wing caused within the Protestant Reformed Church.⁴⁹ Furthermore, the Edict of Torda contributed to the process of confessionalisation of Antitrinitarians, a radical Protestant community that was exceptional in sixteenth-century Europe. As for the secular aspect of this toleration, both Catholics and Protestants could hold public offices in Transylvania, but during John Sigismund's reign, Antitrinitarians were the ones mainly supported in doing so. By 1571, the majority of the Hungarian nobility followed their ruler's example in converting to Antitrinitarianism, for instance the chancellor Mihály Csáky (d. 1572) and the general Kristóf Hagymássy (d. 1577).⁵⁰ In his testament, John Sigismund donated money as well as his own library to the Antitrinitarian school college in Alba Iulia for the purpose of it to a university in later years.⁵¹

To conclude, the root of the Transylvanian denominational plurality and religious tolerance can be regarded as a compromise for the sake of stability – required by the political semi-independence from the Ottoman Empire and the internal conditions of a multi-ethnic, multilingual and multireligious society. As the legitimacy of Transylvanian rulers was subject to the sultan's support and incessantly contested by Habsburg monarchs, they could not allow a social tension to further weaken their power. Importantly, John Sigismund's personal fascination with theology and religious innovations was the key factor in the success of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania, at the court and beyond.

⁴⁹ Mark A. Lampert, *Encyclopedia of Martin Luther and the Reformation*, 2 (London: Rowman & Littlefield, 2017), 615-616.

⁵⁰ Ildikó Horn, "Az unitárius elit stratégiái (1575-1603)," *Keresztény Magvető* 105: (1999), 28-34.

⁵¹ Gusztáv Heckenast, ed., *János Zsigmond végrendelete* (Szeged, 1990), 155-169.

The radicalisation and legacy of Antitrinitarianism, 1571-1588

⁵² Despite the unique degree of religious tolerance in Transylvania, a conflict deriving from theological and political reasons resulted in the extraordinary punishment of Ferenc Dávid. In this last part, we shall analyse the political treatment of the Antitrinitarian radicalisation in the 1570s as well as how it influenced the later history of the denomination.

Image 5: Aladár Körösfői-Kriesch: Ferenc Dávid at the diet of Torda (1896, detail)

In the spring of 1571, John Sigismund died without an heir, and the diet in Alba Iulia elected the most powerful Transylvanian lord to be the next ruler – who was a devoted Catholic. Stephen Báthory (1571-1586) intended to revive the Catholic faith in Transylvania but his aspirations were confined by the influence and contrary interests of the estates.⁵³ Nonetheless, Báthory introduced a few measures to diminish Protestantism, especially the predominant Antitrinitarian community. In September 1571, he restricted the publication of Antitrinitarians' works by abolishing their supervision over the press house in Alba Iulia, and imposed a princely censorship on the printing of every book.⁵⁴ Furthermore, Báthory dismissed Antitrinitarians from leading political positions – Biandrata was allowed to remain a court physician by refraining from his involvement with theological issues. However, as the elite had become mainly Protestant by then, Báthory could not employ a Catholic preacher at the court instead of

⁵² Wikimedia Commons, 2008, accessed May 15, 2020.

⁵³ Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities in East-Central Europe*, 117-118.

⁵⁴ Stephen Báthory's public 'press order', 17 September 1571 in Endre Veress, ed., *Báthory István erdélyi fejedelem és lengyel király*, 1 (Kolozsvár, 1944), 142–143.

Ferenc Dávid, but only a Lutheran one, namely Dénes Alesius (1525-1577).⁵⁵ In his letter to Pope Gregory XIII (1572-1585), the prince stated that Transylvanian Catholicism was in a crisis, and that the ‘Arian sect’ was much more dangerous than the ‘Augsburg confession’ since it was spreading more quickly.⁵⁶ Most importantly, a 1572 diet of the estates accepted Báthory’s initiative, that is to say a decree that forbade any further theological innovations, which was confirmed at two additional assemblies in 1573: ‘If anyone is found believing in anything different and new, they will be excommunicated by His Highness...’⁵⁷ The decree stated that any new ideas born after John Sigismund’s death were considered ‘innovative’. Dávid had already stated in his 1569 *De Regno Christi* that baptism should be preceded by theological teaching, which had been argued in Servet’s *Christianismi Restitutio* as well.⁵⁸ Additionally, Dávid started to elaborate on the theory of radical nonadorantism, the rejection of the adoration of Christ in 1572. Evidently, Dávid’s constant eagerness for theological research contradicted Stephen Báthory’s ‘innovation law’. He complained about their situation getting worse day by day in a letter written on 27 December 1573 to the Greek Antitrinitarian theologian, Jacobus Palaeologus (c. 1520-1585).⁵⁹ As other Antitrinitarians introduced in Chapter 1, Palaeologus had to leave Rome, Geneva as well as Poland-Lithuania because of his nonconformist views, and lived in Transylvania between 1573 and 1575.⁶⁰

⁵⁵ János Erdő, “Adatok az Unitárius Egyház püspökválasztási jogának történetéhez,” *Keresztény Magvető* 82: (1976), 90-97, 91.

⁵⁶ Stephen Báthory to Gregory XIII, 14 September 1574 in Veress, *Báthory István... levelezése*, 298–299.

⁵⁷ ‘... ha külömb és új dolognak vallásában találtatnak, ő nagysága excommunicáltassa...’ Resolutions of the Torda Diet, 25-29 May 1572 in Sándor Szilágyi, ed., *Monumenta Comititalia Regni Transylvaniae*, 2 (Budapest: MTA, 1876), 528.

⁵⁸ Ferenc Dávid, *De Regno Christi Liber primus* (Gyulafehérvár, 1569), appendix: ‘Tractatus de paedobaptismo’, accessed May 22, 2020, http://real-r.mtak.hu/978/1/A_199_II.pdf

⁵⁹ Elek Jakab, *Dávid Ferenc emléke*, 2 (Kolozsvar, 1879), 208.

⁶⁰ Religious nonconformism was shared by several Antitrinitarians as their opinions did not fit the doctrines of any denominations.

March 1578 can be considered a turning point in the development of Transylvanian Antitrinitarianism because paedobaptism, the practice of baptising infants, was rejected at a synod. This step caused a crisis within the Antitrinitarian community since it was disapproved by the ‘conservatives’, including Biandrata. The Italian represented a direct tie to the Polish Brethren so after a series of ineffective internal disputes, he turned to Fausto Sozzini for help by inviting him to Transylvania to change Dávid’s opinion. Sozzini spent five months in Dávid’s house in Kolozsvár, where they debated about the worship and invocation of Christ on the basis of biblical references, without any consensus. In summary, Sozzini claimed that Christ had told that people could turn to him after his Ascension, while Dávid argued that the Son’s power was not equal to the Father’s and that the Holy Scripture did not call for addressing prayers to Christ.⁶¹ Dávid’s most significant supporter during his trial was Palaeologus, who later wrote an extensive essay in defence of Dávid’s nonadorantist views and right to proclaim them.⁶² Ferenc Dávid was arrested for religious innovation on Biandrata’s initiative who, fearing the political ramifications of Dávid’s statements, asked Stephen Báthory to intervene. In June 1579, a diet sentenced the ailing Dávid to imprisonment in the castle of Déva, where he died in November that year.⁶³ After the ‘Dávid case’, Biandrata lost his influence and distinguished position among the Antitrinitarians. In his later years, he reconverted to Roman Catholicism and retired from both written and oral theological disputes. He appointed one of his followers, Demeter Hunyadi (d. 1592) as superintendent of the Antitrinitarians who continued Biandrata’s ‘conservative’, politically cautious religious leadership – especially because Stephen Báthory’s successor, Sigismund Báthory (1586-1602) supported Catholics

⁶¹ “Responsio Fausti Socini”; “Domini Fransisci confutatio responsionis Faustinae” in Mihály Balázs, ed., *Ferenc Dávid: Defensio Fransisci Davidis and De dualitate tracta Francisci Davidis (Cracoviae) 1582* (Utrecht: Bibliotheca Unitariorum; Nieuwkoop: De Graaf, 1983), 4-23, 24-120.

⁶² Balázs, *Ferenc Dávid: Defensio...*, 260.

⁶³ Report about the trial by Catholic priest János Leleszi (c.1548-1595), 9 June 1579 in András Bodor, “Újabb adatok egy négyszázéves perről,” *Korunk* 27: (1968), 1208-1216.

against Protestants to an even greater extent.⁶⁴ Nonetheless, endeavours for further theological research and innovation did not cease with Dávid's death. 'Judaising', the adoption of Jewish tenets and traditions, was a frequent allegation against Antitrinitarians in later decades, particularly when the Sabbatarian movement separated from them. Sabbatarians united Antitrinitarian and Jewish principles and confessed the 'human nature' of Jesus Christ as well as the supremacy of the texts of the Old Testament.⁶⁵

Finally, it is worth looking at a remarkable intellectual accomplishment of an Antitrinitarian in sixteenth-century Transylvania. As this chapter has shown, Stephen Báthory turned against Protestants at the court at the beginning of his reign but soon recognised the limitations of this attitude in an overwhelmingly Protestant environment. He had to release the restrictions and keep his court open to Protestants, even refugees, as long as they proved to be loyal to him. Marcello Squarcialupi (1538-1592) was an Italian Antitrinitarian physician who fled from Italy for 'religionis causa' after his confrontation with the Inquisition. He was employed in Alba Iulia by Báthory between 1579 and 1586 to practice medicine and carry out scientific research.⁶⁶

The princely-supported Squarcialupi studied the aurora borealis, the phenomenon of the northern lights, and wrote its first explanation not based on religious and biblical interpretations, but entirely on scientific observations, calculations and analysis.⁶⁷ Therefore, it can be argued that the main ideas of the Protestant Reformation spread in parallel with the diffusion of humanist culture across Europe.

⁶⁴ Keul, *Early Modern Religious Communities: in East-Central Europe*, 122-124.

⁶⁵ Róbert Dán et al., eds., *Matthias Vehe-Glirius: life and work of a radical antitrinitarian with his collected writings* (Leiden: Brill; Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1982), 18-36.

⁶⁶ Alessandra Quaranta, "Exile Experiences 'Religionis causa' and the Transmission of Medical Knowledge between Italy and German-Speaking Territories in the Second Half of the Sixteenth Century," in *Fruits of Migration: Heterodox Italian Migrants and Central European Culture 1550-1620*, edited by Cornel Zwierlein and Vincenzo Lavenia (Leiden: Brill, 2018), 72-101.

⁶⁷ Miklós Kázmér and Gábor Timár, "Az északi fény első tudományos leírása – Marcello Squarcialupi: De coelo ardore (1580)", *Erdélyi Múzeum* 79: (2017), 82-87.

Image 5: Squarcialupi's observation of a 1577 comet⁶⁸

To sum up, radicalisation was the consequence of Ferenc Dávid's theoretical restlessness that crashed Giorgio Biandrata's wariness regarding the weakened position of Antitrinitarians under the Catholic Stephen Báthory.

⁶⁸ Thomas Erastus, András Dudith, Marcello Squarcialupi and Simon Grynaeus, *De cometis dissertationes novae* (Heidelberg, 1580), 53, own picture.

Conclusion

The radical nature of Antitrinitarianism derived from its Christology. The thoughts of the executed Michael Servetus spread swiftly in northern Italy, particularly in the religiously and intellectually tolerant environment of the University of Padua. Antitrinitarian theology was permeated by medical research and physicians who claimed that the Bible did not justify the veneration of Christ or the Holy Spirit. These statements were incompatible with Catholic theology and Protestant dogmas – both the Inquisition and Calvinist communities regarded them as ‘heretics’ which led to the progress of Antitrinitarianism in exile, in more tolerant areas such as Moravia, Poland-Lithuania and Transylvania.

This paper has demonstrated that the unstable political situation of Transylvania compelled its rulers to maintain the internal peace within the multid denominational society. Additionally, Antitrinitarianism gained significance through John Sigismund’s personal affiliation to the new belief which was a result of the influence of his physician and court preacher, Giorgio Biandrata and Ferenc Dávid. It rose to become the primary religion of Transylvania by 1571 to which the majority of the political elite belonged. Furthermore, the internal conflict of Transylvanian Antitrinitarians emerged because Giorgio Biandrata was contented with the unique legal position that the community had already achieved and preserved even under Catholic rulers, the Báthorys. However, Ferenc Dávid was not willing to conform to these conditions and continued his zealous biblical research to refine his theology. Dávid was sued by the authorities after the unsuccessful attempts of reconciliation made by Biandrata and the Italian theologian Fausto Sozzini. Later, the Antitrinitarian community was led towards a ‘moderate direction’. Antitrinitarian intellectuals continued their activities at the Transylvanian court since the Báthory princes’ endeavours to make Catholicism dominant again were obstructed by the pro-Protestant estates. The Unitarian Church is still one of the main denominations of Transylvania,

and Ferenc Dávid's figure has been preserved as a martyr in Unitarian collective memory. Andrew M. Hill has raised a historiographical debate by positing that Transylvanian Antitrinitarians 'owe more to Michael Servetus than they do to John Calvin'. The paper argues that from a theological point of view, Servet's ideas and, occasionally, complete works did appear in the publications of Biandrata and Dávid. Moreover, their interdenominational issue was a result of Dávid's pursuits of theological research beyond Servetian views, moving even further from Catholicism and Calvinism.

In conclusion, this paper has argued that Antitrinitarianism played a significant and proactive role in Transylvanian religious plurality as it was the primary religion of the elite, including John Sigismund, at the time of the Edict of Torda (1568), the first political document that officially acknowledged freedom of worship as a collective right of communities. The slightly changing religious situation provided a favourable environment for the confessionalisation of the various denominations present in Transylvania. As to further research, it would be beneficial to write a comparative or connected history from a transnational perspective on the development of Antitrinitarianism in Transylvania and Poland-Lithuania since Antitrinitarians faced different political and denominational conditions. At the same time, as this paper has highlighted, several religious radicals were circulating between the two countries, so various personal and intellectual relations could be analysed.

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